

Strengthening Democracy in India: Electoral Reforms, Institutional Interplay & Accountability

Prachi Bagga¹ & Pawanpreet Kaur²

Abstract:

The success of a democratic state is closely related to its governance processes. Election is the basic necessity of democracy as it is the only means to lay down the foundation of representative governance. The integrity of election systems is the cornerstone of democratic society. India being the world's largest democracy, the credibility, transparency and fairness in elections is sine qua non in order to work towards maintaining electoral integrity so as to ensure the will of people in choosing their political representatives. Along with the traditional challenges in elections such as booth capturing, use of money and muscle power etc, the advent of new technological era has embarked various new threats to electoral process. Hence the need for electoral reforms cannot be ignored. Various governments from time to time has brought various reforms to make the process more transparent. Media, being the fourth pillar of democracy has been entrusted with increasing political accountability. The paper discusses the evolution of electoral reforms and various emerging issues such as EVM manipulation, electoral bonds, media manipulation. It highlights the constitutional measures along with legislative efforts that helps resolve these issues and curb malpractices as promoting transparency and accountability in the electoral process is essential for building public trust, confidence and integrity.

Keywords: Electoral Reforms, Transparency, Democratic, Elections, Constitution

Introduction

India, widely regarded as the world's largest democracy, has consistently upheld the principles of free and fair elections since achieving independence in 1947. The democratic process in the country is sustained through periodic elections that are conducted in accordance with the constitutional framework. These elections are not merely routine political exercises but are integral to ensuring representative governance and public participation in decision-making. The responsibility for administering and regulating the

1 & 2 Research Scholar, Department of Laws, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar

electoral process is vested in the Election Commission of India, a constitutionally empowered and independent authority. The Commission is entrusted with the crucial functions of supervision, direction, and control of elections at multiple levels. Its jurisdiction extends to elections for the Parliament and State Legislatures, as well as for the highest constitutional offices, namely the President and the Vice-President of India. The legitimacy and credibility of the electoral process are grounded in strict adherence to constitutional provisions and statutory laws enacted by Parliament. These legal norms provide a comprehensive framework governing voter eligibility, conduct of elections, electoral rolls, and dispute resolution. By operating within this well-defined legal structure, the Election Commission ensures transparency, neutrality, and fairness in the electoral process. Collectively, these mechanisms reinforce public confidence in India's democratic institutions and uphold the foundational values of democracy.

Evolution of Electoral Reforms

After India attained independence in 1947, the framers of the Constitution, particularly Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, established the groundwork for a strong democratic electoral framework. The origins of this process can be traced back to the 1930s, during the Round Table Conferences, where the issue of self-rule for Indians was extensively debated. During this time, Dr. Ambedkar advocated for separate electorates for the Untouchables, similar to those granted to other minority groups. This period saw conflicts such as Gandhi's protest against communal awards,¹ which along with the above led to the country's democratic character and strong reliance on free and fair elections. The forefathers of Indian constitution made sure to learn from the past and thus expressly laid down provisions for free and fair elections in the constitution. Also, with time and changing nature of Indian politics, number of electoral reforms have also been introduced through legislative acts.

Major Electoral Reforms in India

The major electoral reforms in India revolves around ensuring Free and fair elections. The Constitution of India entrusts the superintendence, direction, and control of elections to the Election Commission of India under Article 324, covering elections to Parliament, State Legislatures, and the offices of the President and Vice-President. Articles 325 and 326 further strengthen the democratic process by prohibiting discrimination in the preparation of electoral rolls on grounds such as religion, race, caste, or sex, and by establishing adult suffrage for all citizens above eighteen years of age. Articles 327 and 328 empower Parliament and State Legislatures to enact laws regulating electoral matters, while Article 329 restricts

judicial interference in electoral processes except through election petitions, thereby ensuring smooth conduct of elections.

Complementing these constitutional safeguards are key legislative measures, notably the Representation of the People Act, 1950, which deals with the preparation of electoral rolls, delimitation, and allocation of seats, and the Representation of the People Act, 1951, which governs the conduct of elections, qualifications and disqualifications of candidates, election expenses, corrupt practices, and dispute resolution. Additional statutes such as the Election Commission (Conditions of Service of Election Commissioners) Act, 1991, and the Delimitation Act further reinforce electoral integrity and institutional independence.

The landmark judicial decisions on free and fair elections have played a crucial role in shaping and accelerating electoral reforms in India by filling legislative gaps and strengthening democratic accountability. In *Indira Nehru Gandhi v. Raj Narain (1975)*, by declaring free and fair elections as part of the basic structure of the Constitution, the Supreme Court laid the constitutional foundation for electoral reforms, ensuring that Parliament cannot dilute electoral fairness through constitutional amendments. This judgment reinforced the need for reforms that preserve judicial review, transparency, and equality in elections. In *Mohinder Singh Gill v. Chief Election Commissioner (1978)*, the Court expanded the scope of Article 324, empowering the Election Commission of India to take proactive measures to conduct impartial elections. This interpretation enabled several administrative reforms, such as the Model Code of Conduct, strict monitoring of election expenditure, countermanding of polls due to booth capturing, and use of central forces to ensure neutrality.

Criminalisation In Electoral System

Criminalisation of politics remains a major challenge to India's electoral system, raising serious concerns about the integrity of elected representatives and the quality of governance. Many politicians facing criminal charges continue to exercise influence by using money power and criminal networks, which undermines public trust in the democratic process. Although the Law Commission of India has highlighted the criminal backgrounds of candidates through its reports, the lack of public awareness and effective dissemination of this information limits its impact on voter decision-making. The Representation of the People Act, 1951, particularly Section 8, provides for the disqualification of candidates upon conviction, barring them from contesting elections for six years after conviction. However, weak implementation and delays in the judicial process reduce the effectiveness of this provision.

The increasing role of money in politics further weakens scrutiny mechanisms, allowing candidates with criminal antecedents to enter electoral politics and diluting efforts aimed at ensuring clean, transparent, and accountable elections. As per data from the Association for Democratic Reforms (ADR), 46 per cent of MPs elected in the 2024 Lok Sabha elections (251 out of 543) have pending criminal cases against them, with 31 per cent (170) charged with serious criminal offences, including murder, attempt to murder, and crimes against women to name a few. The corresponding figure for the 17th Lok Sabha stood at 233 (43 per cent) for criminal charges which included 159 (29 per cent) facing serious criminal charges. Thus, the tsunami of criminalisation of politics, far from ebbing, is only rising. This troubling trend is a cause for worry. One must not forget George Bernard Shaw. “Power doesn’t corrupt men; fools, however, if they get into a position of power, corrupt power.”ⁱⁱⁱThe decisions in *Association for Democratic Reforms (2002)* and *PUCL v. Union of India (2003)* directly led to statutory electoral reforms mandating disclosure of criminal antecedents, assets, and liabilities of candidates under the Representation of the People Act, 1951. These judgments transformed electoral reform by recognising informed voting as an essential component of free and fair elections, thereby addressing the problem of criminalisation of politics. Further, *Lily Thomas v. Union of India (2013)* strengthened electoral integrity by enforcing immediate disqualification of convicted legislators, pushing forward reforms aimed at cleansing the political process. Similarly, *Kihoto Hollohan (1992)* underscored the importance of ethical political conduct, indirectly supporting reforms such as tighter anti-defection norms to protect voter mandates. Despite stiff resistance and non-cooperation from Parliament and Executive, Judiciary has carried the flag of electoral reforms through decisions in *ADR vs Union of India (2002)* mandating disclosure of criminal records, *PUCL vs Union of India (2013)* mandating NOTA, *Lily Thomas vs Union of India (2013)* leading to instant disqualification of candidates with conviction, *Public Interest Foundation vs Union of India (2018)* directing parties to publish criminal antecedents of their candidates by print and electronic media and also on their websites along with reasons for selecting such candidates. However, the rising trend of criminalisation of politics, especially the election of separatists in the 18th Lok Sabha, shows that such decisions have achieved little success.

The NOTA

The NOTA (None of the Above) system holds significant importance in Indian elections as it strengthens democratic participation and electoral integrity. By recognising the voter’s right to dissent, NOTA ensures that electors are not compelled to choose a candidate they find unsuitable, thereby preserving the freedom of choice inherent in the right to vote. It encourages greater voter participation by providing an option to express dissatisfaction without abstaining from the electoral process, resulting in a more accurate reflection

of public opinion. Further, NOTA serves as a moral and political signal to parties, indicating public disapproval and pressuring them to nominate candidates with cleaner backgrounds and stronger credibility. By formally recording voter rejection within the electoral system, NOTA promotes transparency and accountability, reinforcing the principles of free and fair elections. The landmark decision in *People's Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India* (2013) marked a significant development in India's electoral jurisprudence by recognising the voter's right to reject all contesting candidates through the "None of the Above" (NOTA) option. In this historic ruling, the Supreme Court affirmed that the right to vote includes the right to dissent, which forms an essential component of free and fair elections. To give effect to this right, the Court directed the Election Commission of India to incorporate a NOTA button on Electronic Voting Machines and ballot papers, allowing voters to formally express their rejection when none of the candidates are found suitable.ⁱⁱⁱ

The Present Scenario

The period from 2014 onwards has witnessed sustained progress and notable reforms in India's electoral framework, shaped by technological advancements, legislative initiatives, and focused efforts to enhance transparency, inclusiveness, and voter participation. This period has largely unfolded under the leadership of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) with Prime Minister Narendra Modi in office. Building upon earlier measures, the Voter Verifiable Paper Audit Trail (VVPAT) system was implemented nationwide from the 2019 general elections, enabling voters to visually confirm their vote through a printed slip before it is securely stored, thereby strengthening transparency and public confidence in electronic voting. The Election Commission of India (ECI) continued updating and purifying electoral rolls through the NERPAP initiative, aimed at removing duplicate entries and improving accuracy by linking voter identification with Aadhaar, despite ongoing concerns related to data privacy. Simultaneously, the ECI explored blockchain-based solutions for remote voting to facilitate participation by migrant workers and non-resident Indians, supported by pilot studies to assess security and feasibility. Electoral reforms during this period also included the introduction of electoral bonds to reform political funding, intended to enhance transparency, though criticised for enabling anonymous donations. The Representation of the People (Amendment) Act, 2018 introduced proxy voting for NRIs, broadening diaspora participation. Monitoring of election expenditure was intensified through surveillance teams and flying squads, while enforcement of the Model Code of Conduct was strengthened using digital tools and social media oversight. Enhanced security arrangements, webcasting from sensitive polling stations, improved accessibility for persons with

disabilities, and targeted initiatives to engage youth and first-time voters further contributed to strengthening the electoral process.

The Recent Controversies Related to Electoral Reforms in India

1. In 2024, The Chandigarh controversy centred on alleged vote tampering during the 2024 Chandigarh mayoral election, sparking widespread debate over electoral integrity. In that election, the returning officer Anil Masih, a nominated councillor was caught on camera invalidating eight votes that had been cast for the Aam Aadmi Party-Congress alliance candidate, allegedly to benefit the rival BJP candidate. The incident was widely condemned and triggered legal challenges claiming manipulation of the electoral process.^{iv}The matter reached the Supreme Court of India, which intervened by ordering the submission and scrutiny of all election records and eventually overturning the earlier result, declaring the AAP-Congress candidate the rightful winner after concluding that the earlier actions were improper. The Court also directed that the eight invalidated ballots be counted.
2. In 2024, EVM manipulation became the burning issue but a Division Bench denied the Association for Democratic Reforms' (ADR) request on April 26, 2024, to cross-check votes cast using Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs) and achieve 100% vote verification through Voter Verified Paper Audit Trail (VVPAT).
3. In 2025, political row has erupted in India over allegations of "vote theft", with opposition parties accusing the country's election body of irregularities, which they say favoured the ruling Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) in the 2024 general elections. On Tuesday, parliament was adjourned after opposition MPs demanded a debate on the integrity of India's electoral process. A day earlier, dozens of opposition leaders, including Congress party leader Rahul Gandhi, were briefly detained by the police in the capital Delhi, as they tried to march to the Election Commission of India's (ECI) headquarters. The Election Commission and the BJP have aggressively rejected the allegations^v. Gandhi referred specifically to Mahadevapura in the Bengaluru Central parliamentary constituency, claiming that the electoral rolls contained over 100,000 irregular entries, including duplicate names, invalid addresses, and mass registrations at single locations. He cited instances such as a voter allegedly casting ballots twice, a claim disputed by the election authorities, and pointed to reports of CCTV footage from polling stations being deleted. He also highlighted cases where dozens of voters were registered at a single address. According to Gandhi, such irregularities cost the Congress nearly 48 seats, amounting to a failure to uphold the principle of "one person, one vote." He has

demanded the public release of digital electoral rolls to enable independent auditing by political parties and citizens.

4. Later in 2025, Opposition claims SIR process being used to disenfranchise minority groups to benefit Narendra Modi's government. India's political opposition has warned that democracy is under threat amid a controversial exercise to revise the voter register across the country, which critics say will disenfranchise minority voters and entrench the power of the ruling Narendra Modi government. A debate erupted in India's parliament last week over the special intensive revision (SIR) process, which is taking place in nine states and three union territories, in one of the biggest revisions of the country's electoral roll in decades^{vi}.

Conclusion

Although there have been collective efforts on the part of government and administrative agencies to ensure proper governance depicting will of people, the new era has been giving rise to new issues that need to be addressed for proper reforms. The constitutional framework along with the legislative measures and collective response of judiciary form the legal backbone of India's commitment to free and fair elections.

ⁱ B. N. Ghosh *Gandhian Political Economy Principles Practice and Policy* Ashgate P.46. 2007

ⁱⁱ <https://adrindia.org/content/electoral-reforms-idea-whose-time-has-come-indian-politics>.

ⁱⁱⁱ People's Union for Civil Liberties & Anr., v/s Union of India & Anr. NO. 161 of SC 2004.

^{iv} Hillary Victor. (2025, 25 June). Anil Masih fiasco fallout: Show of hands, not secret ballot, in next Chandigarh mayoral polls. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/chandigarh-news/anil-masih-fiasco-fallout-show-of-hands-not-secret-ballot-in-next-chandigarh-mayoral-polls-10175079536067>.

^v Neyaz Farooquee. (2025, 13 August). The row over 'vote theft' that has shaken Indian politics. <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c016kg80de5o.amp>.

^{vi} Hannah Ellis-Petersen. (2025, 16 December). India's electoral roll revision threatens democracy and Muslims, say critics. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2025/dec/16/india-electoral-roll-special-intensive-revision-threatens-democracy-muslims>.

Publisher's Note: *The views and opinions expressed in this article are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the publisher, editors, or the editorial board.*